

PRIOR SHAPE ANALYSIS FOR YARN SEGMENTATION IN XCT IMAGES

Hafsa El Herichi ^{1,2,3}, Arturo Mendoza ¹, Yanneck Wielhorski ¹, Hugues Talbot ²
and Stéphane Roux ³

¹Safran Group

Email: hafsa.el-herichi@safrangroup.com, arturo.mendoza-quispe@safrangroup.com,
yanneck.wielhorski@safrangroup.com

² Univ. Paris-Saclay, CentraleSupélec, INRIA, CVN
9 Rue Joliot Curie, 91190 Gif-sur-Yvette, France

Email: hugues.talbot@centralesupelec.fr

³ Univ. Paris-Saclay, CentraleSupélec, ENS Paris-Saclay, CNRS, LMPS
4, avenue des Sciences 91190 Gif-sur-Yvette, France

Email: stephane.roux@ens-paris-saclay.fr

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses the automatic segmentation of textile reinforcements in fan blades using X-ray CT imaging at resolutions above 120 μm . The proposed approach is a scalable analysis orthogonal to the main yarn orientations (warp and weft), involving the identification of yarn centers and cross-sections on a 2D plane.

The method statistically characterizes three properties: the standard shape of yarn cross-sections using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), the continuity of each yarn path, and their arrangement relative to neighbouring yarns. These properties are exploited in a variational formulation for optimal yarn positions, displacement from previous planes, and neighbour arrangements.

Yarn center positions are determined over successive planes perpendicular to the mean yarn orientation, successfully tracking around 1,500 yarns over 900 slices with a 95% success rate for annotated yarns. Then the process iteratively refines segmentation by erasing and re-segmenting yarns. This method shows potential for large-scale textile annotation.

1 INTRODUCTION

This work addresses the automatic segmentation of textile reinforcements in aircraft engine fan blades, imaged with X-ray CT at resolutions above 120 μm with lengths in the tens of centimeters. Previous works have used a variety of approaches ranging from image processing [1], variational methods [2, 3], and deep learning [4, 5, 6].

Yet, these studies focused on smaller samples with simpler geometries and used much higher resolutions.

Applying these approaches to the current problem is not feasible because they would require better image characteristics or expensive initialization, or the computation time would be excessive. Hence, a simple and highly scalable method is proposed based on 2D analysis orthogonal to the main yarn orientations (warp and weft).

2 APPROACH

Here, the segmentation involves identifying the yarn centers and cross sections on a 2D plane based on the known yarn positions from the previous 2D plane. For this study, because of the time-consuming nature of the task, only a subset of yarn centers for a fan blade were manually sparsely annotated.

The proposed method statistically characterizes three specific properties of the material. The first property is the “standard” shape of each yarn cross section (for each yarn type).

For this, a Principal Component Analysis is used on small images centered on the yarn centers. The obtained eigenmodes encapsulate unique, learnable features, leading to the identification of the dominant shape and some of its subtler variations. Hence, cross-correlation between the first eigenmode of each yarn type and the CT images generates a heatmap where higher values correspond to likely yarn centers.

To re-adjust the probable central positions, an alignment between the tomographic image and the principal mode is done by minimizing the squared difference between them, considering both the image and its partial derivatives. Only the positive part of the difference is used to focus on the yarn, ignoring the surrounding background in the image before squaring.

The second property of interest describes the continuous path that each yarn follows. Histograms of contiguous yarn center annotations (for each yarn) are used to model the yarn path “displacement” from one plane to the next. The third property is the specific arrangement of a yarn with respect to its (same type) neighbors. In-plane yarn center annotations are used to model this arrangement. It is observed that parallel yarns follow well-defined orderings. From the above statistics, a variational formulation that includes three energies (figure. 1) is built: the optimal position for each yarn according to the 1 eigenmodes, the most likely displacement from the previous 2D plane, and the position that considers the arrangements between neighboring yarns.

Figure 1: Variational Formulation

Then, an iterative greedy approach is used for successive planes to obtain the new yarn center positions. The initial positions are taken from the previous 2D plane, and at each iteration, the displacement to be applied to each yarn center is computed until convergence.

3 RESULTS

This approach is first applied to warp yarns. Tracking around 1,500 yarns across over 900 slices, with an average success rate of 95% for nearly 400 yarns that have available manual annotations.

Figure 2: Computed warp yarn paths.

The estimated warp yarn paths (figure. 2) are then erased (figure. 3) from the initial CT image, isolating the weft yarns and highlighting segmentation errors, such as yarns lost during tracking. After addressing these issues, the erased image is used to segment the weft yarns using the same procedure. Then, the warp yarns are re-segmented after erasing the weft yarns, and so on. This fixed-point optimization that progressively improves the yarn segmentation is carried out until stationarity is achieved for both yarn directions.

figure (a): original tomography

figure (b): erased warp yarns tomography

Figure 3: Erasing warp yarns in tomographic image.

Finally, 1,500 warp yarns were automatically annotated and tracked over 900 slices, which amounts to 1,350,000 yarn centers. Considering that 11,460 yarn centers were used as initialization (0.85%), the method shows its potential for automatically annotating large-scale textiles. The next development phase will focus on refining the tracking process of weft yarns after the erasure of the retrieved warp paths that currently interfere with accurate tracking. This adjustment is essential to improve the tracking of yarns, ensuring that the algorithm can correctly distinguish and follow weft yarns.

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